

Ani Cathedral: The Reconstruction Process of the Largest Building in Ani

Abstract

This past year, I was enrolled in a Conservation and Preservation course at my university. For my final project, I decided to research the Ani Cathedral, the largest standing structure in eastern Turkey's city of Ani, as a result of my Armenian background and advocacy work. Throughout the centuries, the cathedral, which was originally designed by an architect named Trdat in the 11th century, has crumbled as a result of natural disasters, raids, and cultural conflicts. After unsuccessful restoration efforts ensued within the city of the Ani in the 1990s which threatened its many churches, monuments, and structures, increased transparency was demanded by advocacy groups and governmental organizations worldwide. In 1996, the cathedral was placed on the World Monuments Watch for the first time, and it has been listed numerous times since. In 2016, the Ani Cathedral was officially declared a World Heritage Site by the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), which further drew international attention to the building's need for restoration. In 2011, the World Monuments Fund and the Turkish Ministry of Culture created a formal conservation and preservation project for the Ani Cathedral that is funded by the U.S. State Department. Now, reconstruction efforts have started at the cathedral, although they have been paused due to COVID-19. My paper describes the history of Ani, as well as the history of the cathedral. It touches upon the cathedral's design, significance, and the current restoration project. Research for this project resulted from collaborations with the Metropolitan Museum of Art, Tufts University, and Yavuz Özkaya (the project's restoration architect in Turkey). Moreover, this paper relies on literature reviews, articles, and interviews with Özkaya. This paper contains many images and information about the site that have yet to be officially published due to my

correspondence with Yavuz Özkaya, who sent over multiple videos, photo albums, and information pertaining to the present day reconstruction efforts.

Main Paper

The city of Ani, located in the remote highlands of northeast Turkey, possesses a rich and vibrant cultural past. Between 961 and 1045, the city functioned as the capital of the Bagratid Armenian kingdom. At the same time, Ani gained prominence in the 10th and 11th centuries due to being located on many major trade routes and acting as an essential component of the Silk Road. During its prime, Ani possessed over 100,000 residents. However, the city lost some of its splendor after undergoing multiple periods of turmoil. Specifically, Ani was sacked by the Mongol Turks in 1236.¹ Then, less than a hundred years later in 1319, there was a large earthquake that led to further destruction. Over the years, the city was occupied by a variety of different kingdoms and empires, including the Byzantines and the Ottomans. However, the city was abandoned during the early 1700s and only reoccupied when it was annexed by Russia after the 1877-1878 war between the Russians and the Ottoman Empire. Then, during World War I and the Armenian Genocide, the city was abandoned yet again. Over the years, the remains of Ani were destroyed by looters, poor restoration attempts, and even Turkish individuals who tried to remove traces of Armenian history from the area.²

¹ SILK ROADS Dialogue, Diversity & Development.” UNESCO. Accessed April 10, 2020. <https://en.unesco.org/silkroad/content/archaeological-site-ani-was-inscribed-unesco-world-heritage-list>.

² “ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITE OF ANI.” Turkish Cultural Foundation. Accessed April 24, 2020. <http://www.turkishculture.org/archaeology/ani-1104.htm>.

Picture of Ani³

Over the last hundred years, Ani has once again been deemed an important site, and the remains of the city have attracted attention on an international level. Moreover, it is considered to be the largest cultural heritage site in Eastern Turkey. Specifically, in relation to conservation and preservation, excavations and restorations in Ani began again during the 1990s with the support of the Turkish Ministry of Culture and Tourism. However, this attempt at restoration was not considered successful; instead, it led to widespread backlash. For one, the restorations were considered overly aggressive. Another reason for the controversy was that the entire route to restoration was very poorly documented. However, interestingly enough, churches were not the focus of the renovation projects, and thus were neglected. However, as a result of these renovation efforts jeopardizing buildings in Ani, advocacy efforts began that prompted the protection of the city's architecture. In turn, the World Monuments Fund started to work to preserve Ani's historic past. Overall, the failures of the 1990s preservation efforts led to

³ "ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITE OF ANI." Turkish Cultural Foundation. Accessed April 24, 2020. <http://www.turkishculture.org/archaeology/ani-1104.htm>.

increased scrutiny on the city's buildings and their future restoration efforts. Moreover, this ensured that future restoration efforts would be better documented and more transparent.

Modern day Ani is currently in the middle of a widespread restoration and preservation campaign. The campaign itself is the result of various organizations collaborating. It is led by the Republic of Turkey's Ministry of Culture and Tourism, supported by a partnership between the Turkish Ministry of Culture and Tourism and the World Monuments Fund, and financed partially by the US Department of State's Ambassadors Fund for Cultural Preservation. As a result, the backing for this effort spans multiple nations. Since 2006, restoration processes throughout the city have been occurring. These include preliminary site management and capacity building workshops with local and regional stakeholders.⁴

Photo of Ani Cathedral Within Ani, Credit to Yavuz Özkaya (Restoration Architect)⁵

It is important to recognize that the restoration processes taking place in Ani have various political implications, especially when taking into account the strained relationships between Turkey and Armenia. As Ani is a town with a rich, vibrant Armenian past, it is important that the restoration processes taking place preserve past elements that contributed to the city's historic value. In other words, any restoration processes should maintain the authenticity of the original architectural structures. However, Turkey and Armenia have historically contested each

⁴ Watenpaugh, Heghnar Z. "The Cathedral of Ani, Turkey: From Church to Monument." *Sacred Precincts*, January 2015, 460–73. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004280229_027.

⁵ Yavuz Özkaya

other's viewpoints, especially in regard to the past. The main example of this is the Armenian Genocide, the massacre of 1.5 million Armenians by Turkish individuals between 1914 and 1923. To this day, this event is not recognized by the government of Turkey as a genocide, and Turkish individuals in the United States continue to protest formal recognition by American governing bodies.⁶ This creates conflicting viewpoints in regard to what structural elements of buildings in Ani should be preserved or not. Moreover, the reconstruction process is made even more difficult as a result of the site's remote location, seismic activity, and the poor status of the region of Kars.⁷

Drone Photography of North Walls of Ani in Kars Region⁸

This brings us to the focus of this paper, the most iconic building in Ani, which is the Ani Cathedral. Its 2015 World Heritage Nomination file claims that “with its pointed arches, clustered columns and four free standing piers, the Cathedral of Ani is one of the most impressive examples of the inscribed cross plan during the early medieval period.”⁹ The building is 113 feet long and 81 feet wide. Before the cathedral underwent significant destruction over the years, it stood 125 feet tall and was the tallest structure within the city of Ani. The cathedral is

⁶ Bayraktar, Seyhan. “The Politics of Denial and Recognition: Turkey, Armenia and the EU.” *The Armenian Genocide Legacy*, 2016, 197–211. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-137-56163-3_13.

⁷ “Preserving the Medieval City of Ani.” *Journal of the Society of Architectural Historians* 73, no. 4 (2014): 528–55. <https://doi.org/10.1525/jsah.2014.73.4.528>.

⁸ Yavuz Özkaya

⁹ “Ani Cultural Landscape World Heritage Nomination File.” UNESCO, (2015).

<http://whc.unesco.org/uploads/nominations/1518.pdf>

considered one of the sources of inspiration for Gothic architecture, especially due to its usage of pointed arches and vaults, as well as its clustered piers. Structurally, the cathedral is a domed basilica with a central plan.

Reconstruction Plan for Cathedral, Credit to Yavuz Ozkaya (Restoration Architect)¹⁰

The building is held up by pendentives, as well as the intersection of four barrel vaults. It is made entirely of stone. The outward facing portion is made of well cut and polychrome stone, while the internal elements are composed from a rubble concrete core. The exterior features a decorative arcade placed upon columns that runs around its entirety. The north, south, and west walls all contain doorways that act as entrances which feature vaulted porches. Each transept contains small pothole windows underneath its gables. The cathedral's inside is tall and purposely dark, and its apse and side chambers make up about a fourth of the interior space. There are four piers in the nave that supported the dome before its destruction; these also

¹⁰ Yavuz Özkaya

support the arches that hold up the roof. There are also barrel vaults running alongside the east-west and north-south axes of the cathedral.¹¹

Design Details of Exterior of the Cathedral¹²

Design Details of Interior¹³

Over the years, specific details of the cathedral have been changed to hide traces of the building's Armenian past. For instance, there are large gaps in the interior stonework that most likely contained khachkars, Armenian cross-stones, before they were removed. Moreover, Armenian inscriptions have been deliberately hidden as a result of efforts by the Turkish government through added paint coverings that match the stonework. As a result, the Ani Cathedral now has many of the details of its original interior obscured.¹⁴

¹¹ www.virtualani.org. "Armenian Architecture - VirtualANI - The Cathedral of Ani." VirtualANI. Accessed May 7, 2020. <http://virtualani.org/cathedral/index.htm>.

¹² Yavuz Özkaya (Restoration Architect)

¹³ Yavuz Özkaya (Restoration Architect)

¹⁴ www.virtualani.org. "Armenian Architecture - VirtualANI - The Cathedral of Ani." VirtualANI. Accessed May 7, 2020. <http://virtualani.org/cathedral/index.htm>.

The cathedral is structurally composed of reddish, blackish, and brownish aslars (masonry made of large square-cut stones). It is a three aisled basilica with a central dome which is supported by four large free-standing columns. These carried the collapsed dome through the use of pendentives. The inside of the cathedral contains vaults and arches. There are semicircular arched entrance doors to the west, north, and south of the cathedral that were made for the people, the patriarch, and the king. All entrance doors possessed small porches at the front which were attached to cathedral walls. The main apse has two story high vaulted chapels on either side. Massive columns rising up to support the ceilings and the dome are main elements as well.¹⁵

In regard to the building's significance, the cathedral, which was built between 989 and 1001 by one of the most famous Armenian architects, Trdat, has occupied various roles of importance throughout past centuries. After being commissioned by the Bagratid dynasty, the church was turned into a mosque. Then, it returned to acting as an Armenian Apostolic Church. The cathedral is the largest church in Ani and excavations in 1908 by Nicolai Marr revealed other buildings surrounding the cathedral. For instance, in the east, there is a sepulchre where Queen Katrenide is believed to be buried, and the southeast corner contains a baptistery building. To the west and south of the cathedral, there is a cemetery.¹⁶

Over the years, as the city crumbled due to invasions and natural disasters, the cathedral's structure broke down as well. For instance, during a 1319 earthquake in Ani, the cathedral's conical roof collapsed. Then, another earthquake that occurred during the early 1800s led to the destruction of the cathedral's drum. One more earthquake in 1988 heavily damaged the cathedral's northwest corner, creating a large hole. It also led to damage in the

¹⁵ Yavuz Özkaya (Restoration Architect)

¹⁶ Yavuz Özkaya (Restoration Architect)

southwest corner. By 1998, parts of the cathedral's roof had begun to fall, and the entire building was in danger of collapsing if restoration efforts were not initiated. Moreover, the cathedral was even further damaged by explosions in an Armenian quarry that shook the ground of Ani during the early 2000s. These blasts continued until 2009 and further destroyed the cathedral's structure. The loss of the cathedral's central dome as a result of these destructive periods has led to the building having a cube shaped form.¹⁷

Damage to the Cathedral as Seen in 2012 Before Restoration Began¹⁸

To put this all into context against initial restoration and preservation efforts, in 1996, the Ani Cathedral was placed on the World Monuments Watch for the first time. Every other year, the World Monuments Watch selects at-risk heritage sites to be placed on this list, and the Ani Cathedral has been placed on it multiple times for its historical significance and modern day social impact. Specifically, it has been listed in 1996, 1998, 2000, and 2002. Since the Ani Cathedral achieved this designation, the World Monuments Fund has started a documentation, conservation, and preservation program to stabilize the building. Moreover, to adequately understand the cathedral's construction, the World Monuments Fund conducted a laser survey

¹⁷ www.virtualani.org. "Armenian Architecture - VirtualANI - The Cathedral of Ani." VirtualANI. Accessed May 7, 2020. <http://virtualani.org/cathedral/index.htm>.

¹⁸ Yavuz Özkaya (Restoration Architect)

in 2006 through the use of three dimensional laser scanning. This high definition digital survey technology revealed both the internal and external construction elements of the cathedral without the need for excavation.¹⁹

**Example of the Deformations Discovered Through Digital Survey Technology
(West Facade)²⁰**

In 2009, an agreement was reached between Turkish authorities and the World Monuments Fund that led to preliminary plans regarding Ani Cathedral's stabilization and protection. However, it is important to note that Turkey's decision to cooperate with the conservation and preservation efforts was mainly due to a desire to make Ani into a tourist site, which would in turn lead to accrued revenue. As such, the final stage of the restoration will involve increasing public awareness of the cathedral and improving conditions to the extent that visitors can enter to view the building. As a result of this agreement, plans were made between the World Monuments Fund and Anadolu Kültür, a nonprofit cultural institution located in Turkey, for reinvigorating the cathedral. To touch upon further efforts supporting the cathedral's

¹⁹ Gharipour, Mohammad. *Sacred Precincts: the Religious Architecture of Non-Muslim Communities across the Islamic World*. Leiden: Brill, 2015.

²⁰ Yavuz Özkaya (Restoration Architect)

reconstruction, In 2010, the Global Heritage Fund also recognized Ani as a heritage site in danger of disappearing alongside eleven other sites. In 2011, the World Monuments Fund and the Turkish Ministry of Culture created a formal conservation and preservation project for the Ani Cathedral that is funded by the U.S. State Department.²¹ In 2012, as a result of monitoring efforts, a drone was sent around the site to take photos.

Photo of Ani Cathedral Taken in 2012²²

In 2013, a workshop called “Ani in Context” was held at Ani which was sponsored by the Turkish Ministry of Culture and Tourism and the World Monuments Fund. During the event, experts researched the need for restoration in regard to each monument and structure in Ani. To do this, they developed a Risk Assessment Matrix and then evaluated twenty eight structures. The Risk Assessment Matrix included many factors including heritage significance, intactness of building, exterior significant fabric, interior significant fabric, and archaeological remains. Then, in 2016, the Ani Cathedral was officially declared a World Heritage Site by the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), which further drew international attention to the building’s need for restoration. In March 2015, a structural health monitoring

²¹ Palak’ean, Grigoris, Peter Balakian, and Aram Arkun. *The Ruins of Ani*. New Brunswick, NJ: Rutgers University Press, 2019.

²² Yavuz Özkaya (Restoration Architect)

system was installed which led to plans for construction material analyses, excavations, cataloging, repair and completion of roof tiles, and resolving the drainage problem.²³

Şekil 6: Doğu Yünü Dış Kısmı Sensörlerinin (2 Adet Çatlak Ölçer, 1 Adet Eğim Ölçer) Genel Görünüşleri

Photos of Installation of Structural Health Monitoring System in 2015 (East)²⁴

As seen through the efforts promoting the Ani Cathedral's structural stability and architectural integrity, this process has spanned years. As of now, the current restoration efforts are being overseen by a restoration architect named Yavuz Özkaya. While Christina Maranci, a Tufts University Professor who also directed me to resources for this project, put me in touch with Yavuz, and his knowledge was invaluable. Sources state he is employing scientific approaches in regard to the restoration and wants to remove some previous reconstructions to ensure the integrity of the site. He has displayed disappointment in regard to the excavations of the 1990s; for instance, in regard to the gate to the City of Ani, he is quoted as saying it "used inappropriate materials, notably excessive cement containing soluble salts that contaminated

²³ Documents from Yavuz Ozkaya

²⁴ Yavuz Özkaya (Restoration Architect)

the original remains; it severely compromised the ancient structure by adding more load than it could bear; and it created a drainage problem.”²⁵

Since Özkaya has taken over the reconstruction projects in Ani and become responsible for reversing the damage, an entirely new design philosophy has come into effect. This strategy focuses on stabilization and protection through proposals like the addition of shelter roofs. The restoration process of the cathedral has been planned in three stages and the approach to the restoration is phased. Before any stage began, imaginary drawings were created to show the original shape of the cathedral to ensure accuracy. Moreover, as every stage progresses, further excavations, research, and monitoring takes place.

As of now, only the first stage has been completed. This involved excavations, temporary emergency measures including scaffoldings outside and inside, structural health monitoring, and taking inventory of the fragments around the cathedral. A fence was installed and temporary load bearing scaffolding was placed along the west and south walls. A protective load bearing wooden scaffolding was also placed inside the cathedral to protect it from potential damage. They excavated and cataloged fragments on the roofs as well.²⁶

²⁵ Watenpaugh, Heghnar Z. “The Cathedral of Ani, Turkey: From Church to Monument.” *Sacred Precincts*, January 2015, 460–73. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004280229_027.

²⁶ Yavuz Özkaya (Restoration Architect)

Temporary Emergency/Protective Measures During Stage One (2018)²⁷

Temporary Emergency/Protective Measures During Stage One (2018)²⁸

The second stage will start after COVID-19 ends. It will involve the stabilization of the walls and weakened elements of the structural system. Specifically, the second stage will be

²⁷ Yavuz Özkaya (Restoration Architect)

²⁸ Yavuz Özkaya (Restoration Architect)

targeting demolished parts of the cathedral including its northwest corner, especially in regard to the walls, ceiling, and roof. Engineering measures will also go into effect to help repair the detached walls and ceiling. It will involve the reparation of roof tiles and resolve the drainage problems in the cathedral.²⁹

Stage Two Progress in Regard to Cleaning, Cataloguing, and Stabilizing Roof (Present)³⁰

The third phase will involve reconstructing the conical dome atop the cathedral and partially repairing the gates. However, the third phase is not fully planned out yet and will be

²⁹ Yavuz Özkaya (Restoration Architect)

³⁰ Yavuz Özkaya (Restoration Architect)

determined in greater detail after the roofs are fully cleaned. To ensure that the reconstruction is accurate, Özkaya has pledged that while repairing the roofs and masonry, they will make sure everything is the same original size and material. This stage will be further enhanced by new findings, comparative analyses and data evaluation.³¹

Conclusion

The Ani Cathedral, as a building of great religious and cultural significance, must be restored properly to ensure the survival of the structure over hundreds of years. The three step plan in place will help ensure the cathedral's longevity, but transparency is crucial. As such, further efforts should be made to document and research further developments in regard to the Ani Cathedral's restoration process.

³¹ Yavuz Özkaya (Restoration Architect)

More Photos

Phase One of Reconstruction Diagram³²

Third Phase (Dome Closing) Proposal³³

Reconstruction Drawings – Sections & West Porch³⁴

³² Yavuz Özkaya (Restoration Architect)

³³ Yavuz Özkaya (Restoration Architect)

³⁴ Yavuz Özkaya (Restoration Architect)

Reconstruction Drawings: North and West Elevations³⁵

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³⁵ Yavuz Özkaya (Restoration Architect)

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